

Proper exercise filter during epidemics such as Covid 19

Dr. Fereshteh Amouzadeh- PhD in Sports Psychology

Considering that The use of masks in athletes causes hypoxic and hypercapnic breathing as evidenced by increased effort during exercise and The use of masks during a short exercise with an intensity around 6–8 METS, decreases O₂ by 3.7% and increases the CO₂ concentration by 20%. And on the other hand regular practice of adequate intensity is suggested as an auxiliary tool in strengthening and preparing the immune system for epidemics such as COVID-19.

It seems that **making a filter** that does not get wet in sports activities and does not cause respiratory problems can help to do physical activities in epidemics and thus strengthen the immune system of people. This filter can cover all or part of the face and is very light and made of smart fabrics.

It seems that the use of new methods such as **smart fabrics** for **making proper exercise filter** may be beneficial for improving the immune system in all people Especially athletes.